

Notes

Copper(II) Complexes with *N*-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amino Acids

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IN continuation of our studies¹ on metal complexes of *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine, we report herein the isolation and characterisation of copper(II) complexes with some other *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amino acids, viz. α -alanine, valine, leucine, isoleucine, phenylalanine, tyrosine, tryptophan and histidine.

Experimental

Potassium salt of the ligands were isolated by reported method².

Synthesis of copper(II) complexes: An aqueous solution (30 ml) of copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate (1.24 g, 0.005 mol) was added to a solution of potassium salt of *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amino acids (0.005 mol) in 90% methanol (50 ml) and pH was adjusted 7.0–7.5 with acetic acid. The green solution was refluxed for 1 h, concentrated to about 50 ml and allowed to cool. The resulting green crystals were washed successively

with 10 ml portions of water, ethanol and ether, and dried under reduced pressure (70–80%).

Elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic, electronic, ir and epr spectral data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the ligands showed a band at ~ 410 nm, characteristic of quinoneimine structure³. Ir spectral data ($\nu_{C=O} \approx 1630$, $\nu_{C=N} \approx 1540$ cm^{-1}) are also in agreement with this structure. Thermogravimetry showed clearly that a water molecule is preferentially expelled from the complexes in the temperature range 180–200°.

Visible spectra of the complexes showed a weak broad band at ~ 630 nm with weak shoulders at ~ 570 and ~ 750 nm. Together with the magnetic moment data, this indicated square-planar geometry for the complexes⁴.

The $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ bands were observed in the spectra of the complexes at ~ 1620 and ~ 1570 cm^{-1} respectively. The observed $\Delta\nu_{COO}$ was consistently > 200 cm^{-1} ($\nu_s(\text{COO}) = 1605 \pm 5$, $\nu_a(\text{COO}) = 1390 \pm 10$ cm^{-1}) which indicated unidentate coordination by the carboxylate group⁵. The broad band centred at ~ 3450 cm^{-1} was evidently due to coordinated water. Far-ir spectra of the complexes showed medium intense band at 500–520 cm^{-1} (M–N) and 400–430 cm^{-1} (M–O).

Esr spectra of the complexes in the solid state were typical axial spectra with two *g* values which

TABLE 1 – ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND ESR SPECTRAL DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % :		μ B.M.	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Esr spectra		
	Found/(Calcd.)				$g_{\parallel}$	$g_{\perp}$	g_e
	Cu Found (Calcd.)	II Found (Calcd.)					
[Cu(Nap : α -ala)(H ₂ O)]	19.35 (19.69)	4.44 (4.34)	1.85	2.3	2.272	2.066	2.137
[Cu(Nap : val)(H ₂ O)]	18.00 (18.12)	3.81 (3.99)	1.79	1.3	2.253	2.061	2.125
[Cu(Nap : leu)(H ₂ O)]	17.37 (17.42)	3.69 (3.84)	1.83	2.1	2.279	2.073	2.142
[Cu(Nap : leu ⁱ)(H ₂ O)]	17.49 (17.42)	3.62 (3.84)	1.78	1.1	2.251	2.067	2.128
[Cu(Nap : phe)(H ₂ O)]	15.81 (15.94)	3.22 (3.51)	1.89	0.9	2.273	2.068	2.136
[Cu(Nap : tyr)(H ₂ O)]	15.13 (15.32)	3.21 (3.38)	1.80	2.2	2.301	2.071	2.148
[Cu(Nap : try)(H ₂ O)]	14.40 (14.52)	6.31 (6.40)	1.87	2.0	2.269	2.067	2.134
[Cu(Nap : his)(H ₂ O)]	16.51 (16.35)	10.93 (10.81)	1.92	2.9	2.267	2.070	2.134

*In the abbreviations used for *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amino acidates (2-) moiety, the part derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde is denoted by Nap and that from the amino acid by the first three letters of its name.

indicated a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state and an essentially square-planar arrangement around copper(II). The trend, $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ observed for the complexes, indicated that the unpaired electron is most likely in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of copper(II). This is further supported by the ratio⁶, $(g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2) \approx 4$. From the observed g values, it is evident that the metal-ligand bonds have considerable covalent character⁷. Spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{Nap}:\text{gly})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ recorded in DMF showed four main peaks, evidently due to coupling of the electron with the ^{63}Cu nucleus ($I=3/2$). The peaks are broad and have the appearance of ill-resolved triplets. The breadth and triplet appearance, attributable to hyperfine splitting by nitrogen atom ($I=1$) of the ligand, provide evidence for nitrogen coordination⁸. The resolution is poor, presumably due to recording at room temperature. The $\tilde{A}_{\text{Cu}}$ values observed (ca. 85G) for these chelates are comparable to those of the similar copper(II) complexes for which delocalisation of metal d -electron to the chelate ring has been envisaged⁹.

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Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Piperidinomethylurea

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THE present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with piperidinomethylurea, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}-\text{CO}-\text{NH}_2$ (PMU). Kinetic parameters of the non-isothermal decompositions of a selected few complexes and PMU have also been reported.

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Experimental

PMU¹ was prepared by reacting a 37% aqueous HCHO (20.3 g) and urea (15.0 g) mixture with piperidine (21.25 g) at $\sim 10^\circ$. The metal salt (0.02 mol) and PMU (0.02 or 0.04 mol) were dissolved separately in a suitable organic solvent (30 ml; BuOH, DMF etc.) and the two solutions were mixed and stirred at $\sim 80^\circ$ and pH ~ 7 . The resulting solid metal complex formed was washed with the hot solvent followed by ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator (Table 1). Molar conductance, infrared and electronic spectra both in solid (MgCO_3) as well as in solution (DMF) and room temperature magnetic susceptibility were measured for characterising the complexes. TG and DTA studies were carried out upto 1200° at a heating rate of 10° under static air.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF PMU COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		Metal	Anion	N
$\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$	Green	14.10 (13.23)	15.35 (15.98)	18.55 (18.93)
$\text{NiBr}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$	Green	10.85 (11.03)	30.64 (30.01)	15.37 (15.77)
$\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Green	16.75 (17.28)	- (36.50)	19.31 (20.61)
$\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Green	15.20 (14.16)	- (47.97)	9.91 (10.13)
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Brown	22.45 (21.80)	24.30 (24.33)	13.95 (14.41)
$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU}$	Greenish blue	14.65 (14.17)	16.25 (15.81)	19.22 (18.73)
$\text{CuBr}_2 \cdot \text{PMU}$	Brown	16.25 (16.70)	41.05 (42.02)	11.36 (11.04)
$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blue	12.75 (11.82)	- (23.07)	22.25 (20.84)
$\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Blue	10.65 (10.37)	- (32.48)	13.92 (13.71)
$\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Greenish blue	17.75 (18.02)	28.25 (27.23)	11.76 (11.91)

Results and Discussion

The complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with PMU are green and blue or brown respectively. They are slightly soluble in common organic solvents. The low molar conductance values ($1.9 - 3.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) indicate the non-ionic nature of the complexes except in the cases of $\text{CuX}_2 \cdot 2\text{PMU} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4$) which are 1 : 2 electrolytes ($145 - 149 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ in DMF and $54.5 - 58.9 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$).

In all the complexes, the carbonyl stretching vibrational mode of the free ligand observed at 1630 cm^{-1} experiences a negative shift of $30 - 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the bonding of PMU to the metal through oxygen². The peaks at $1155 - 1120 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\nu_{\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{O}}$ of the piperidine ring of PMU) get lowered by $80 - 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes pointing to the